

NUMERACY SKILLS AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS MATHEMATICS OF STUDENTS IN RELATION TO PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION PROGRAM

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 33

Issue 2

Pages: 167-185

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3150

DOI: 10.70838/pemj.330204

Manuscript Accepted: 02-05-2025

Numeracy Skills and Attitude Towards Mathematics of Students in Relation to Performance: Basis for Intervention Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the numeracy skills and attitudes towards mathematics of grade 7 students and their relationship to academic performance in mathematics. The study employed a correlational research design involving 210 Grade 7 students selected through a multistage random sampling technique. Data were collected using a numeracy skills test, an attitude towards mathematics questionnaire, and students' mathematics performance in SY 2023-2024. The results showed that most students had nearly proficient numeracy skills, a very favorable attitude towards mathematics, and a satisfactory mathematics performance. A significant positive correlation was found between numeracy skills and mathematics performance, but no significant relation was found between attitude toward mathematics and mathematics performance. Further analysis revealed that numeracy skills and attitude toward mathematics significantly predict performance. Based on these findings, an intervention program was developed to enhance the numeracy skills and improve the attitude towards mathematics of grade 7 students, ultimately improving their performance in the subject. The intervention program includes targeted instruction, hands-on activities, and strategies to foster a positive mindset toward mathematics.

Keywords: *numeracy skills, performance level, attitude towards mathematics*

Introduction

Every student can learn, although their pace and methods of learning may vary (Schmitz, 2022). Mastering mathematics is not straightforward for everyone; many students find it challenging. Each learner has a unique approach to grasping concepts, which is why teachers need to recognize and accommodate these individual differences and needs. Ignoring these variations can hinder the effectiveness of both teaching and learning (Hebres, 2022).

Educators have conducted comprehensive studies on students' attitudes toward Mathematics (Chen et al., 2018). Those with a positive outlook typically find enjoyment in the subject, acknowledge its significance, and exhibit confidence in their abilities, which motivates them to prioritize studying it (Kiwanuka, H. N., Van Damme, J., Van Den Noortgate, W., & Reynolds, C. 2020). This positive attitude can lead to higher performance in mathematics. Students who enjoy and feel confident in mathematics are more inclined to persist through challenges and achieve better results (Cho & Hwang, 2019). Furthermore, as noted by Hebres, RB (2022) the academic performance of students is linked to their level of numeracy, as numeracy assessments require the application of mathematical concepts learned from kindergarten to Grade 10 across multiple subjects.

In the recent student assessment of 15-year-old learners across 79 countries done by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the Philippines ranked in the low 70s in the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) in Mathematics and Science. This is very alarming because the number of non-numerates is increasing. As educators, we can innovate, make intervention programs, or create instructional materials to capacitate the students in the different mathematical skills.

Numerous other research has investigated students' attitudes toward Mathematics, yet a person-centered approach, which examines different patterns or combinations of variables for each profile, has seldom been used. Although some studies have investigated profiles of students' attitudes toward Mathematics, they often did so in conjunction with other constructs. For instance, Berger et al. (2020) analyzed the attitudes of 10,051 Austrian eighth-grade students toward Mathematics and science using latent profile analysis (LPA), identifying six profiles.

This prompted the researcher to investigate more on the influence of students' attitudes towards Mathematics and their numeracy skills on future academic success, particularly in Math achievement.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the attitude towards mathematics and numeracy skills of the Grade 7 students of Mansilingan Agro-Industrial High School in SY 2023-2024 in relation to their mathematics performance. Specifically, this research study aimed to find answers to these questions:

1. What is the profile of grade 7 students in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. type of elementary school they graduated;
 - 1.3. average family monthly income; and
 - 1.4. parent's highest educational attainment?

2. What is the level of numeracy skills of grade 7 students when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile?
3. What is the level of attitude towards mathematics of the grade 7 students when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile?
4. What is the level of performance in mathematics of the grade 7 students in terms of the profile?
5. Is there a significant difference in the numeracy level of grade 7 students when grouped according to profile?
6. Is there a significant difference in the level of attitude towards mathematics of grade 7 students when grouped according to profile?
7. Is there a significant difference in the performance of the respondents in mathematics when grouped according to profile?
8. Is there is a significant relationship between the numeracy level and the performance level in mathematics of grade 7 students?
9. Is there a significant relationship between the attitude towards mathematics and the level of performance in mathematics of grade 7 students?

Methodology

Research Design

This study investigated the numeracy skills and attitudes towards Mathematics and their relationship to academic performance in Mathematics of the Grade 7 students in Mansilingan Agro-Industrial High School in SY 2023-2024. The study employed a descriptive correlational research design involving 210 Grade 7 students selected through a multistage random sampling technique. Descriptive statistics refers to the process of summarizing numerical and categorical data in a concise and informative manner (Green et al.,2023). In this study, the frequency, weighted mean, and percentages were used to present the respondent's sex, the type of elementary school they came from, average family income, parents' highest educational attainment, attitude towards Mathematics, and numeracy skills.

This study employed a survey research design, specifically suited for conducting an assessment survey. The descriptive-correlational method was chosen to describe variables and measure the relationships between them. The research focused on exploring the relationships between respondents' attitudes towards mathematics, their numeracy skills, and their performance in mathematics.

Respondents

The subject and respondents of the study were the Grade 7 students of Mansilingan Agro-Industrial High School enrolled in school year 2023-2024.

Instrument

To collect the necessary information for this study, the following data gathering instruments were employed:

To determine the attitude of the respondents towards mathematics, a survey questionnaire adopted from Tapia (1996) was used. The questionnaire included two parts; the first part was about the profile of respondents including the sex, type of elementary school graduated, family monthly income and parent's highest educational attainment. The second part was about their attitude towards Mathematics. There were a total 20 items under the Attitude towards Mathematics Inventory (ATMI). The students responded to a given item by checking the description (very strongly agree, strongly agree, agree, disagree, or strongly disagree) which best describes/represents their thought.

For the Numeracy test, the researcher used the standardized numeracy assessment tool crafted by Department of Education (DepEd) which were being administered to students in the beginning of the school year.

The standardized numeracy assessment tool consisted of forty items focusing on the four fundamental operations with integers. This tool was administered across all schools in the division of Bacolod City.

To evaluate the students' Academic Performance in Mathematics, the researcher computed the final average rating for the first semester, which was composed of grades from two grading periods (first and second). This assessment adhered to DepEd Order no. 31 s. 2020, "Interim Guidelines for Assessment and Grading in Light of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan." The grading scale and descriptors used were: 90-100 interpreted as outstanding; 85-89 as very satisfactory; 80-84 as satisfactory; 75-79 as fairly satisfactory; and 75 and below as did not meet expectations.

Following the numeracy assessment, results were compiled, tabulated, and accurately interpreted using frequency counts and an interpretation table as part of the data analysis procedure to determine the students' achievement or performance in mathematics.

Procedure

In the process of gathering data, the researcher secured approval from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bacolod (refer to Appendix A.1) as well as from the school head (see Appendix A.2). Following these approvals, the researcher distributed survey forms to assess students' attitudes toward mathematics (see Appendix F). The numeracy test was administered in two phases: the pre-test took place during the second week of November 2023, while the mid-test was conducted in the last week of February 2024, with assistance from the Grade 7 Math teachers.

Before the numeracy test, the researcher provided an orientation to the students, outlining the test's objectives and general instructions. During this orientation, the researcher emphasized the importance of adhering to specific guidelines, including the prohibition of calculators, cell phones, and other electronic devices during the 12-minute test period. The test was administered during the students' scheduled math classes.

Ethically, the researcher ensured the confidentiality and anonymity of all participants. Each answer sheet was personally collected by the researcher, achieving a 100% retrieval rate. This careful approach not only safeguarded the students' responses but also reinforced the integrity of the data collection process. Following the collection, the students' responses were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted in collaboration with the researcher's statistician, ensuring accurate and reliable results.

Data Analysis

After the data was gathered, the researcher tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted it. The following statistical tools were used in analyzing and interpreting the data.

For problem number 1, on the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, average family monthly income, type of school graduated, and parent's educational attainment frequency and percent distribution were used.

For problem number 2, on the level of numeracy skills of Grade 7 students when grouped according to profile, mean was used.

For problem number 3, on the level of attitude towards Mathematics of the Grade 7 students when grouped according to profile, mean was used.

For problem number 4, on the Performance level in mathematics of the grade 7 students in terms of profile, mean was be used. Moreover, the researcher used DepEd Order no.31 s.2020 "Interim Guidelines for Assessment and Grading in Light of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan" as bases in which the final rating is interpreted using the grading scale.

For problem number 5, on the significant difference in the level of numeracy skills of Grade 7 students when grouped according to profile, Mann-Whitney or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test and Kruskal-Wallis test were used.

For problem number 6, on the significant difference in the attitude towards Mathematics of secondary students when grouped according to profile, Mann-Whitney or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test and Kruskal-Wallis test were used.

For problem number 7, on the significant difference in the Performance of the respondents in Math when grouped according to profile Mann-Whitney or Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test and Kruskal-Wallis test were used.

For problem number 8, on the significant relationship between the numeracy level and the performance level in Mathematics of Grade 7 students, a Gamma Coefficient was used.

For problem number 9, on the significant relationship between the attitude towards Mathematics and performance level in Mathematics of grade 7 students Gamma Coefficient was used.

Results and Discussion

This section underscores the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered in this research study. The results are presented in tables to emphasize the significant meaning of each problem.

Distribution of Respondents According to Profile

The table 2 below shows the distribution of respondents according to profile.

Table 2. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Respondents According to Profile

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
Sex	Male	110	52.38
	Female	100	47.61
	Total	210	100.00
Average Monthly Family Income	₱10,001 & Above	35	16.67
	₱5,001- ₱10,000	77	36.67
	₱5,000 and below	98	46.67
	Total	210	100.00
Type of School	Public	205	97.62
	Private	5	2.38
	Total	210	100.00
Parents Educational Attainment	Elementary level	4	1.90
	Elementary Graduate	2	.95
	High School level	37	17.62

High School Graduate	50	23.81
College Level	39	18.57
College Graduate	78	37.14
Total	210	100.00

Based on the table, in terms of sex, 110 out of 210 respondents, or 52.38 percent are male, while approximately 100, or 47.61 percent are female. The data suggested a 4.77 percent higher representation of male students compared to females, indicating a dominance of male students among grade 7 attendees.

In terms of the type of elementary school they graduated, most grade 7 students, comprising 205 out of 210 respondents, or 97.62 percent, attended public schools. Conversely, only about 5 students, or 2.38 percent, received their primary education from private institutions. This data underscored the prevalence of students from public school backgrounds among grade 7 attendees.

In terms of average family income, most of the respondents, comprising 98, or 46.67 percent, belong to a family with average monthly income of ₱5,000 and below (Low Income). This is followed by 77 respondents, or 36.67 percent, come from a family with income ranging from ₱5,001 to ₱10,000 (Middle Income). Additionally, 35 respondents, or 16.67 percent of the total, report a monthly income of ₱10,001 and above. The table highlighted that most grade 7 students at Mansilingan Agro-Industrial High School come from families with income of ₱5,000 or less.

Finally, when it comes to the highest educational attainment of the parents, the distribution of educational attainment among respondents revealed that the highest frequency, comprising 6 respondents, or 2.85 percent, have parents who reached elementary level; 41.43 percent or 87 have parents who reached high school level and 55.71 percent or 117 have parents who reached college level. This data underscored the varied educational backgrounds of parents surveyed in the study.

Level of Numeracy Skills

The table below shows the level of numeracy skills of grade 7 students when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile.

Table 3. *Level of Numeracy Skills of Grade 7 Students when taken as a whole and when grouped according to Profile*

Profile	Category	n	mean	Interpretation
Sex	Male	110	53.29	Nearly proficient
	Female	100	56.025	Nearly proficient
Average Monthly Family Income	₱10,001 & Above	35	54.64	Nearly Proficient
	₱5,001 - ₱10,000	77	54.25	Nearly proficient
	₱5,000 and below	98	54.85	Nearly proficient
Type of School	Public	205	54.73	Nearly proficient
	Private	5	49	Low proficient
	Elementary level	4	47.5	Low proficient
	Elementary Graduate	2	56.25	Nearly proficient
Parents Educational Attainment	High School level	37	55.95	Nearly proficient
	High School Graduate	50	52.95	Nearly Proficient
	College Level	39	55.64	Nearly proficient
	College Graduate	78	54.81	Nearly proficient
As a Whole		210	54.60	Nearly proficient

The table above showed the level of numeracy skills of Grade 7 students when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile variables which are sex, average family income, type of schools they graduated and parent’s highest educational attainment.

When taken as a whole the respondents gained an average numeracy skill of 54.60 which indicates nearly proficient. When grouped according to sex, both male and female have an average numeracy skill that indicates a nearly proficient level with 53.29 and 56.025 mean scores respectively. From these statistics, we can observe that, on average, female students scored slightly higher than male students in numeracy tests.

The findings contrast with those of Van Tetering et al. (2019), which indicated that boys generally outperformed girls in Mathematics across various grade levels from 7 to 12 years old. Additionally, boys demonstrated superior performance in spatial mental rotation skills. When students are grouped according to the type of elementary school they graduated from, students who graduated from public schools had a mean score of 54.73 indicating a Nearly proficient score while those who graduated from private schools only scored a 49 mean score indicating low proficient. It can be viewed that those from public schools scored higher than those from private schools.

When grouped according to average family income, students from low-income family had the average numeracy skills of 54.85 indicating nearly proficient while those students from middle income scored 54.25, nearly proficient and those from high income family

scored a 54.64, also interpreted as nearly proficient. Lastly, when grouped according to their parent's highest educational attainment, students whose parents are elementary level got 47.5, indicating low proficient, respondents whose parents are elementary graduates got a mean of 56.25 indicating nearly proficient, high school level got 55.95, nearly proficient and college level had an average numeracy skill of 55.64 still indicating nearly proficient and finally the college graduate group got an average numeracy of 54.81, also indicating nearly proficient.

Based on the above data, it can be observed that regardless of the average family income, students scored nearly proficient numeracy level; moreover, in terms of the type of elementary schools, those who graduated in public schools have remarkably higher numeracy skills than those who graduated from private elementary schools; it can also be observed that parents' highest educational attainment did not really matter to the average numeracy skills of the students because all the levels got an average numeracy that indicated nearly proficient.

Contrary to the findings, Logaos and delos Santos (2020) identified a significant positive moderate relationship between parental support and Mathematics performance, validated at the 0.05 significance level. This underscores that parental support significantly contributes to students' Mathematics performance. It is recommended that parents consistently provide support to their children. Furthermore, implementing parental enhancement programs can strengthen family relationships and further enhance student performance.

Lastly, Clerkin and Gilligan (2018) established a link between early numeracy activities at home during young children's development and their attitudes towards Mathematics, as well as their mathematical achievement by fourth grade. Their study found that engaging in numeracy activities early in childhood significantly and positively influenced attitudes towards Mathematics by fourth grade. Children who were exposed to math activities early on tended to develop more positive attitudes towards Mathematics, which persisted through at least fourth grade. Conversely, students with negative attitudes towards Mathematics in fourth grade tended to perform at lower academic levels. This highlights the critical role of early math exposure in shaping attitudes and subsequent academic achievement in Mathematics.

Level of Attitude towards Mathematics

The table below shows the level of attitude towards Mathematics of grade 7 students when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile.

Table 4. *Level of Attitude towards Mathematics of Grade 7 Students when taken as a whole and when grouped according to Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Sex	Male	110	3.63	Favorable attitude
	Female	100	3.54	Favorable attitude
Average Monthly Family Income	₱10,001 & Above	35	3.55	Favorable attitude
	₱5,001-₱10,000	77	3.56	Favorable attitude
	₱5,000 and below	98	3.61	Favorable attitude
Type of School	Public	205	3.59	Favorable attitude
	Private	5	3.33	Neither favorable nor unfavorable attitude
	Elementary level	4	3.74	Favorable attitude
	Elementary Graduate	2	3.22	Neither favorable nor unfavorable attitude
Parents Educational Attainment	High School level	37	3.65	Favorable attitude
	High School Graduate	50	3.62	Favorable attitude
	College Level	39	3.54	Favorable attitude
	College Graduate	78	3.55	Favorable attitude
As a Whole			3.58	Favorable attitude

The table above showed, the attitude towards Mathematics of grade 7 students in Mansilingan Agro-Industrial High School when taken as a whole and when grouped according to the variable sex, type of elementary school, average family income and parents' highest educational attainment.

When taken as a whole, the attitude of the respondents towards Mathematics gained a mean of 3.58, indicating favorable attitude. In terms of sex, male students got an overall mean of 3.63 while female got a mean of 3.54 both are indicating favorable attitude. In terms of the elementary school they graduated, those who came from public schools got a mean of 3.59 which indicates favorable attitude while those who came from private schools got a mean of 3.33 which indicates neither favorable nor unfavorable attitude towards Mathematics. In terms of average family income, all groups, high income, middle income and low income got a mean indicating favorable attitude with means of 3.61, 3.56, and 3.55 respectively. Finally, in terms of parents' highest educational attainment, those whose parents are elementary level got a mean of 3.74, indicating favorable attitude, elementary graduate got a mean of 3.22, indicating neither favorable nor favorable attitude, high school level got a mean of 3.65, indicating favorable attitude, high school graduate got a mean of 3.62, indicating favorable attitude, college level got a mean of 3.54 and college graduate got a mean of 3.55 still indicating

favorable attitude.

The figures above only implied that when taken as a whole and when grouped according to the identified profile variables, generally, the respondents had favorable attitude towards Mathematics. It can be meant that Mathematics is not a subject in school that respondents hate or have negative impression on rather it is something that they like learning. Overall, students displayed a positive attitude towards Mathematics when categorized by gender. However, a small percentage of students showed a negative attitude. It is important not to overlook these students, as cultivating positive attitudes is crucial for effective Mathematics learning.

The result of this study is in consonance with the study of Shah and Nazir (2023) who explored the impact of students' attitudes towards Mathematics on their mathematical achievement at the secondary school level that highlighted those psychological and environmental factors, including home environment, peer group dynamics, classroom climate, and exposure to mass media, can significantly influence students' attitudes towards Mathematics.

Creating a conducive learning environment for counting at home involves parents facilitating their children's learning, providing motivation and appreciation, and supplying age-appropriate teaching materials or learning media (Abbas et al., 2019). Economic conditions significantly impact children's learning support, including their motivation and appreciation, which are influenced by the family environment. In rural areas, where economic status is often lower-middle class, children frequently exhibit lower motivation to learn (Cahya Rila et al., 2019). Thus, economic circumstances play a critical role in shaping children's educational experiences and opportunities for learning at home.

Furthermore, Subia, et.al (2018) noted that a positive attitude towards Mathematics reflects a favorable emotional disposition towards the subject, whereas a negative attitude indicates the opposite. These emotional dispositions significantly influence individual behavior, as individuals are more likely to excel in subjects they enjoy, feel confident in, or find useful. Therefore, fostering positive attitudes towards Mathematics is crucial, as they can enhance motivation and willingness to learn.

Level of Performance in Mathematics

The table below shows the level of performance in mathematics of Grade 7 students when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile.

Table 5. *Level of Performance in Mathematics of Grade 7 Students when taken as a whole and when grouped according to Profile*

Profile	Category	n	mean	Interpretation
Sex	Male	110	85.15	Very Satisfactory
	Female	100	86.67	Very Satisfactory
Average Monthly Family Income	₱10,001 & Above	35	86.06	Very Satisfactory
	₱5,001 - ₱10,000	77	86.51	Very Satisfactory
	₱5,000 and below	98	85.31	Very Satisfactory
Type of School	Public	205	85.80	Very Satisfactory
	Private	5	89	Very Satisfactory
	Elementary level	4	85	Very Satisfactory
	Elementary Graduate	2	82	Satisfactory
Parents Educational Attainment	High School level	37	85.78	Very Satisfactory
	High School Graduate	50	85.76	Very Satisfactory
	College Level	39	86.33	Very Satisfactory
	College Graduate	78	85.91	Very Satisfactory
As a Whole		210	85.87	Very Satisfactory

The table shows the performance level of Grade 7 students when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile variables which are sex, average family income, type of schools they graduated and parent's highest educational attainment.

When taken as a whole, the respondents gained an average performance in mathematics of 85.87 which indicates very satisfactory. When grouped according to sex, male respondents got an average of 85.15 while female got an average of 86.67 which are both interpreted as very satisfactory.

When taken according to the type of elementary school they graduated from, those who came from the public school got an average of 85.80 while those who graduated from a private school got an average of 89, both mean averages indicated very satisfactory.

On the average family income, students belonging to low- income family had the average performance of 85.31; middle-income family children had the average performance of 86.51 and those from the high-income family had the average performance of 86.06 respectively. All mean averages indicated very satisfactory.

Lastly, when grouped according to their parents' highest educational attainment, students whose parents' highest educational background is elementary level got a performance in Mathematics of 85 indicating very satisfactory level, elementary graduate got a mean of 82, indicating satisfactory, high school level got a mean of 85.78, indicating very satisfactory, high school graduate got a mean

of 85.76, indicating very satisfactory, college level got a mean of 86.33, indicating very satisfactory and college graduate got a mean of 85.91, indicating very satisfactory level.

From the above statistics, we can observe that, on average, female students performed slightly better than male students in Mathematics; those who graduated in private school also performed better than those from public school, those students belonging to middle-income and high-income family performed better than those who belong to low-income family. Those students whose parents are elementary graduates had lower performances than those whose parents are high school and college levels.

Furthermore, numerous studies have sought to explain the "male advantage" observed in early-grade Mathematics performance. Alongside gender stereotypes, researchers have investigated domain-general and domain-specific cognitive variables as potential explanations for gender differences. For instance, Van Tetering et al. (2019) demonstrated that boys generally outperform girls in Mathematics across various grade levels among children aged 7 to 12 years old. Additionally, boys exhibited superior performance in spatial mental rotation skills compared to girls. These findings highlight cognitive factors that may contribute to the observed gender differences in mathematical achievement during early schooling years.

Difference in the Level of Numeracy Skills According to sex

The table 6.1 below shows the difference in the level of numeracy skills of Grade 7 students when grouped according to Sex.

Table 6.1. *Difference in the Level of Numeracy Skills of Grade 7 Students according to Sex*

Sex	N	Mean Rank
Male	110	97.70
Female	100	114.09
Total	210	

Computed (U) value: 4641.5

P-value: 0.05

Decision: Reject Ho

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on the analysis of the data presented in the table, there were 110 male students and 100 female students. The mean numeracy skills level for male was 97.70, while female it was 114.09. With a computed (U) value of 4641.5 and a corresponding p-value of 0.05, the results revealed no significant difference in the mean numeracy level of students when grouped according to their sex at 0.05 significance level, hence, hypothesis was accepted. It can be concluded that on average, respondent's numeracy level did not differ based on sex.

The result above implied that both male and female respondents did not make any difference in their numeracy level. That sex does not define how one works well with numbers.

The result above was like the findings that Ayebo and Dingle (2021) found that both male and female have the same numeracy level. That their sex does not in any way affect their numeracy level. Research showed that gender gaps in Mathematics carry on after high school. For instance, males in the United States regularly score higher on the mathematics section of the Scholastic Aptitude Test (SAT) than their female counterparts. Also, in Turkey, males in college outperformed females in Mathematics (Saygin, 2020).

Difference in the Level of Numeracy Skills According to Average Family Monthly Income

The table 6.2 on the next page shows the difference in the level of numeracy skills of Grade 7 students when grouped according to average family monthly income.

Table 6.2. *Difference in the Level of Numeracy Skills of Grade 7 Students according to Average Family Monthly Income*

Average Family Monthly Income	N	Mean Rank
₱10,001 & Above	35	110.59
₱5,001- ₱10,000	77	111.21
₱5,000 and below	98	99.20
Total	210	

Computed (H) value: 2.002

P-value: 0.367

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The findings indicate the level of numeracy skills among students grouped by family income. The mean ranks for students with family incomes of ₱10,001 & above, ₱5,001- ₱10,000 and ₱5,000 and below are 110.59, 111.21 and 99.20, respectively. The computed (H) value of 2.002, with a corresponding p-value of 0.367, suggests that there is no significant difference in the numeracy level of students when grouped according to average family income at 0.05 significance level. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be concluded that on average, respondents' numeracy level did not differ based on their average family income.

Hence, it can be noted from the above results that no matter how much money their family earns, that does not make them good or bad

in math. Regardless of if they come from a low-income family, middle-income family, or high-income - family, their numeracy level was the same.

Strickland et al. (2020) on the other hand, found that children's participation in numeracy activities at home and the kindergarten level offers a noticeable boost to their performance at higher levels. For instance, Aunio et al. (2019) examined 442 first-grade students in South Africa and found that perceptive and language skills, as well as the opportunity to learn Mathematics in pre-school, are crucial factors that influence students' numeracy skills in the first grade.

Integrating informal and formal early math and numeracy activities into daily life at home and school effectively prepares children for elementary school Mathematics. Parents and educators play pivotal roles in utilizing play, games, books, songs, and daily conversations to enrich learning experiences. Establishing a language-rich environment and intentionally incorporating academic language are crucial strategies to build a strong foundation in elementary math. Introducing and consistently reinforcing mathematical academic language is particularly beneficial in instructing and intervening for at-risk students. Both parents and educators share the responsibility of providing diverse and engaging numeracy learning opportunities for children, thereby supporting their overall mathematical development.

As noted by Jailani (2019), learning to count at home is inseparable from the family environment, which serves as the primary educational center for children and significantly influences their numeracy development. Additionally, the family's economic situation significantly impacts children's education. Parents facing economic challenges may struggle to meet their children's educational needs, potentially diverting children's focus towards family obligations rather than education.

Difference in the Level of Numeracy skills According to Type of school

The table 6.3 below shows the difference in the level of numeracy skills of Grade 7 students when grouped according to type of school.

Table 6.3. *Difference in the Level of Numeracy Skills of Grade 7 Students according to Type of School*

Type of School	n	Mean Rank
Public	205	106.39
Private	5	69
Total	210	

Computed (U) value: 330

P-value: 0.171

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The data in Table 6.3 presents an analysis of student numeracy skills based on the type of school they attend, comparing public and private institutions. The sample includes 205 students from public schools with an average score of 106.39 and five students from private schools with an average score of 69. The computed (U) value of 330, with a corresponding p-value of 0.17, suggests that there is no significant difference in the mean numeracy level scores of students when grouped according to the type of elementary school they came from at the 0.05 significance level. Hence, we can imply that the type of elementary school they graduated from or have been trained in in their formative years did not matter to the numeracy level of the respondents.

In contrast to previous studies, such as research among Asian secondary school students, which indicated that Asian students often harbor negative attitudes towards Mathematics due to societal expectations from teachers and parents (Uchida & Mori, 2018), further validating studies are needed to confirm these findings.

Regarding private school students, factors unrelated to resource constraints but recognized in research literature as correlating with higher academic achievement include access to ICT resources at home, emotional support from parents, a growth mindset, and cooperative classroom environments. However, despite these positive influences theoretically supporting academic success, some private school students may still struggle in Mathematics for various reasons. For example, emotional support from parents might be perceived as unconditional, regardless of academic performance, potentially reducing motivation to strive harder. A fixed mindset about intelligence could lead students to believe that poor math performance does not reflect their overall intelligence or self-worth, diminishing their drive to improve. Moreover, perceiving a cooperative classroom environment might cause some students to rely more on peers rather than developing individual problem-solving skills in Mathematics. These hypotheses warrant further investigation in future research (Bernardo et al., 2022) to comprehensively understand how these factors contribute to diverse academic outcomes among private school students in Mathematics.

Difference in the Level of Numeracy Skills According to Parent's Educational Attainment

The table 6.4 shows the difference in the level of numeracy skills of Grade 7 students when grouped according to parent's educational attainment.

It presents an analysis in the level of numeracy skills among students categorized by their highest educational attainment. The mean ranks for students with educational attainments at elementary level, elementary graduate, high school level, high school graduate, college level and college graduate are 63.75, 125, 112.73, 96.23, 113.31 and 105.75, respectively. The computed (H) value of 4.48,

with a corresponding p-value of 0.482, suggests that there is no significant difference in the mean numeracy scores of students when grouped according to their parents' highest educational level at the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. In conclusion, it can be inferred that, on average, the numeracy level of respondents was not influenced by their parents' highest educational attainment.

Table 6.4. *Difference in the Level of Numeracy Skills of Grade 7 Students according to Parent's Educational Attainment*

<i>Parent's Educational Attainment</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Elementary level	4	63.75
Elementary Graduate	2	125
High School level	37	112.73
High School Graduate	50	96.23
College Level	39	113.31
College Graduate	78	105.75
Total	210	

Computed (H) value: 4.48

P-value: 0.482

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

However, Bektaş and Hunt (2020) cited Rubinsten et al. (2018) who identified several risk factors associated with the development of math anxiety. These include Within-child predispositions: Brain functioning, Genetics, generalized anxiety, Threat-related attentional bias, Poor past performance in Mathematics, Environmental factors that may act as mediators or moderators in the development of math anxiety: Parents' insecurity about Mathematics and their own deficient numerical skills.

Difference in the Level of Attitude According to Sex

The table 7.1 below shows the difference in the level of attitude towards Mathematics of Grade 7 students when grouped according to sex.

Table 7.1. *Difference in the Level of Attitude Towards Mathematics of Grade 7 Students according to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Male	110	110.37
Female	100	100.15
Total	210	

Computed (U) value: 4964.5

P-value: 0.223

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The findings indicate the level of attitude towards Mathematics among students grouped sex. The mean ranks for students from male was 110.37 while female it was 100.15. The computed (U) value of 4964.5, with a corresponding p-value of 0.223, suggests that there is no significant difference in the mean attitude level of students when grouped according to their sex at the 0.05 significance level, hence, hypothesis was accepted. It can be concluded that on average, respondents' attitude towards Math did not differ based on sex. The above figures only revealed that both sexes have the same attitude towards learning Mathematics.

The result above agreed with the findings of Ayebo and Dingle (2021) who stated that there was no statistically significant difference between men and women for the mathematics attitude scales, except for liking, where men reported higher scores than women. Thus, Mathematics educators need to examine practices and policies to try to understand the reason behind the existence of the gender imbalance. There may be instructional practices that unintentionally contribute to the gender difference.

Furthermore, Anokye-Poku & Ampadu, (2020) revealed in their study that, in general, both female and male students held positive attitudes towards Mathematics, and there was no significant difference in attitudes between genders toward Mathematics. However, the results established that there was a significant difference in achievement. It was recommended that to achieve sustainable development goal 4, teachers, parents, and educational authorities should develop creative and innovative ways of helping students, especially female students to build self-confidence in the learning of Mathematics.

Difference in the Level of Attitude According to Average Family Monthly Income

The table 7.2 shows the difference in the level of attitude towards mathematics of Grade 7 students when grouped according to average family monthly income.

The findings indicate the level of attitude towards Mathematics among students grouped by family income. The mean ranks for students with family incomes of ₱10,001 & above, ₱5,001- ₱10,000 and ₱5,000 and below are 103.91, 102.56 and 108.38, respectively. The computed (H) value of 0.425, with a corresponding p-value of 0.809, hence, the result was not significant. It can be concluded therefore, that on average, respondents' attitude towards Mathematics did not differ based on their average family income at the 0.05 significance level.

Table 7.2. Difference in the Level of Attitude Towards Mathematics of Grade 7 Students according to Average Family Monthly Income

Average Family Monthly Income	N	Mean Rank
₱10,001 & Above	35	103.91
₱5,001- ₱10,000	77	102.56
₱5,000 and below	98	108.38
Total	210	

Computed (H) value: 0.425

P-value: 0.809

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Since math is not a subject that is widely taught in early childhood, parents and teachers should focus on tutoring their preschool-age children. By also incorporating literacy activities into my tutoring sessions, their children will be able to learn more about both numeracy and literacy (Harris & Petersen, 2019). This would also give another avenue to share ideas and activities with parents for continued support at home.

Difference in the Level of Attitude According to Type of School

The table 7.3 below shows the difference in the level of attitude towards mathematics of Grade 7 students when grouped according to type of school.

Table 7.3. Difference in the Level of Attitude Towards Mathematics of Grade 7 Students according to Type of School

Type of School	N	Mean Rank
Public	205	106.15
Private	5	78.90
Total	210	

Computed (U) value: 379.5

P-value: 0.322

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The findings indicate the level of attitude towards mathematics among students grouped by type of school. The mean ranks for students from public schools was 106.15 while for private schools was 78.90. The computed (U) value of 379.5, with a corresponding p-value of 0.322, suggests that there is no significant difference in the mean attitude level of students when grouped according to the type of elementary school they were from at the 0.05 significance level. It can be concluded therefore, that on average, respondents' attitude towards Math did not differ based on the type of elementary school they came from.

However, the above results do not support the key among its findings in the study of Mohammed & Abdul-Razak, (2018) that showed the role school-types could play in altering the gender-related differences in attitudes towards Mathematics. Female students from mixed-gender schools appeared to report lower levels of Mathematics competence/self-belief than those in single-sex schools, as the latter actively perceive that Mathematics is useful and do not think that Mathematics is a male domain.

Moreover, Ersan & Rodriguez (2020) revealed that SES is a strong predictor of Mathematics achievement between schools. Even though previous researchers indicated that there might be more influence of school variables on achievement than SES in low-income countries, also known as the Heyneman–Loxley effect, it was not observed such an effect in Turkey. Instead, it was seen that schools whose students come from economically and socially wealthier families also had a more positive school environment and higher achievement that increased educational inequity in the country.

Lastly, Devi and Reddi (2023) claimed that there are notable differences in students' mathematical attitudes about gender, location, school type, teaching medium, and achievement. To improve the mathematical attitudes of students studying in government schools, Telugu-speaking schools, rural schools, and low achievers in mathematics, facilities and training should be made available to the pupils.

Difference in the Level of Attitude According to Parent's Educational Attainment

The table 7.4 shows the difference in the level of attitude towards mathematics of Grade 7 students when grouped according to parent's educational attainment.

The findings indicate the level of attitude towards mathematics among students categorized by their highest educational attainment. The mean ranks for students with educational attainments at elementary level, elementary graduate, high school level, high school graduate, college level and college graduate are 123.88, 60.50, 111.59, 112.05, 100.78 and 100.98, respectively. The computed (H) value of 3.086, with a corresponding p-value of 0.687, suggests that there is no significant difference in the mean attitude level of students when grouped according to their parents' highest educational level at 0.05 significance level. It can be concluded that on average, respondents' attitude towards Math did not differ based on their parents' highest educational attainment. It only implied that the respondents' attitude towards Mathematics was not based on their parents' highest educational level. It doesn't matter if their

parents have graduated or reached college level, high school or just finished their elementary level, that did not do anything to change their attitude towards Mathematics. In other words, their favorable attitude towards Mathematics was not affected by their profile variables.

Table 7.4. *Difference in the Level of Attitude Towards Mathematics of Grade 7 Students according to Parent's Educational Attainment*

<i>Parent's Educational Attainment</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Elementary level	4	123.88
Elementary Graduate	2	60.50
High School level	37	111.59
High School Graduate	50	112.05
College Level	39	100.78
College Graduate	78	100.98
Total	210	

Computed (H) value: 379.5

P-value: 0.322

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

In contrast with the findings above, Hidayatullah & Csikos (2020), found that academic performance and motivation were also closely associated with a personal background like parents' educational background (PED). According to prior research, PED is consistently associated with students' Mathematics performance. Students with a higher level of PED tend to have better achievements (Dixson et al., 2018) because parents with high educational backgrounds tend to be more involved in their children's studies. Besides, research indicated that PED determines students' academic motivation.

Difference in the Level of Performance in Mathematics According to Sex

The table 8.1 below shows the difference in the level of performance in mathematics of Grade 7 students when grouped according to sex.

Table 8.1. *Difference in the Level of Performance in Mathematics of Grade 7 Students according to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Male	110	92.87
Female	100	119.39
Total	210	

Computed (U) value: 4111

P-value: <0.001

Decision: Reject Ho

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The findings indicate the level of performance in Mathematics among students grouped sex. The mean ranks for students from male was 92.87 while 119.39 from female. The computed (U) value of 4111, with a corresponding p-value of <0.001, suggests that there is a significant difference in the performance in Mathematics of students when grouped by their sex at the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Consequently, it can be concluded that, on average, the level of performance in Math among respondents was influenced by their sex. Thus, sex is identified as one of the determinants of their Mathematics performance.

Many studies have investigated the "male advantage" observed in early-grade Mathematics performance, exploring both gender stereotypes and cognitive variables as potential factors. For example, Van Tetering et al. (2019) demonstrated that boys generally outperform girls in Mathematics across various grade levels among children aged 7 to 12 years old, particularly excelling in spatial mental rotation skills. These findings suggest that both cognitive factors and domain-specific skills may contribute to the observed gender disparities in mathematical achievement from early childhood onward.

Conversely, Tanghal and Tanghal (2022) found a significant positive relationship ($r = 0.263$) between sex and academic performance among students. Their study indicated that females tend to outperform males in subjects like English I and in the mathematical performance of the common first year at CLSU. However, Hathella and Priyanath (2021) reported that while males generally exhibit higher Mathematics performance than females, the difference was not statistically significant ($p > .05$), suggesting that gender alone may not be a decisive factor in Mathematics achievement when other variables are considered. These contrasting findings underscore the need for further research to better understand the nuanced factors influencing gender differences in Mathematics performance.

Difference in the Level of Performance in Mathematics According to Average Family Monthly Income

The table 8.2 shows the difference in the level of performance in mathematics of Grade 7 students when grouped according to average family monthly income.

The findings indicate the level of performance in Mathematics among students grouped by family income. The mean ranks for students with family incomes of ₱10,001 & above, ₱5,001- ₱10,000 and ₱5,000 and below are 112.09, 114.81 and 95.83, respectively. The computed (H) value of 4.787, with a corresponding p-value of 0.091, suggests that there is no significant difference in the level of Math

performance among students when grouped according to their average family income at the 0.05 significance level. As a result, the null hypothesis was accepted. This suggests that, on average, the Math performance level of respondents was not significantly influenced by their average family income. It can be noted then, that one's Math performance cannot be defined by one's family's statuses.

Table 8.2. *Difference in the Level of Performance in Mathematics of Grade 7 Students according to Average Family Monthly Income*

<i>Average Family Monthly Income</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
₱10,001 & Above	35	112.09
₱5,001- ₱10,000	77	114.81
₱5,000 and below	98	95.83
Total	210	

Computed (H) value: 4.787

P-value: 0.091

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Marine Hascœt, et.al (2020) opposed to the results above showing that, while controlling for children's previous Mathematics achievement, their final Mathematics achievement was influenced by children's Mathematics self-concept, the family socioeconomic and educational context, and parental expectations regarding their children's academic achievement. The findings also highlighted that Chilean parents base their expectations on parents' capacity to support their children's education as much as on their children's previous academic achievement.

Furthermore, family factors that influence students' Mathematics achievement encompass aspects of the family's socioeconomic background, including parents' education and occupation, as well as the educational resources accessible within the home (Lam and Zhou, 2021; Marks and Pokropek, 2019). These studies underscore the significant impact of familial socio-economic contexts and educational support structures on students' performance in Mathematics.

Difference in the Level of Performance in Mathematics According to Type of School

The table 8.3 below shows the difference in the level of performance in mathematics of Grade 7 students when grouped according to type of school.

Table 8.3. *Difference in the Level of Performance in Mathematics of Grade 7 Students according to Type of School*

<i>Type of School</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Public	205	104.29
Private	5	155.20
Total	210	

Computed (U) value: 264

P-value: 0.062

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The findings indicate the level of performance in Mathematics among students grouped by type of school. The mean ranks for students from public was 104.29 while 155.20 from private schools. The computed (U) value of 264, with a corresponding p-value of 0.062 suggests that there is no significant difference in the level of Math performance among students when grouped according to the elementary school they attended at the 0.05 significance level. This suggests that there was no significant difference in the performance of the respondents regardless of whether they came from a public or private school.

Moreover, the 2018 PISA Mathematics assessment (OECD, 2019) highlighted significant disparities in Mathematics learning outcomes among Filipino high school students. The results indicated that many students, particularly those in Philippine public high schools, were not achieving the expected learning standards in Mathematics.

On average, private school students scored at Level 1 proficiency, whereas students from public schools scored below Level 1. Specifically, approximately 3 out of every 10 private school students scored below Level 1 proficiency in Mathematics, whereas this number increased to 6 out of every 10 for public school students. These findings underscore the notable differences in mathematical proficiency between students in private and public schools in the Philippines based on the PISA assessment.

As noted by Dakwar (2022), in his study Academic Performance in Mathematics of High School Students with Virtual Instruction vs. Face-to-Face Instruction, it was found that no significant difference exists between the means of "Percentages of Students Scoring at the Proficient Level in TCAP Math Tests" across students attending schools located in economically disadvantaged counties and students attending schools located in economically non-disadvantaged counties. The difference is not considered significant since a p-value = 0.0667, which is greater than the designated significance level 0.05, was reported with the "Economically Disadvantaged County Yes and No".

Difference in the Level of Performance in Mathematics According to Parent’s Educational Attainment

The table 8.4 on the next page shows the difference in the level of performance in mathematics of Grade 7 students when grouped according to parent’s educational attainment.

Table 8.4. *Difference in the Level of Performance in Mathematics of Grade 7 Students according to Parent’s Educational Attainment*

<i>Parent’s Educational Attainment</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Elementary level	4	90.63
Elementary Graduate	2	79.75
High School level	37	103.11
High School Graduate	50	104.36
College Level	39	110.82
College Graduate	78	106.13
Total	210	

Computed (H) value: 0.999
P-value: 0.963
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

It presents an analysis in the level of performance in Mathematics among students categorized by their highest educational attainment. The mean ranks for students with educational attainments at elementary level, elementary graduate, high school level, high school graduate, college level and college graduate are 90.63, 79.75, 103.11, 104.36, 110.82 and 106.13, respectively. The computed (H) value of 0.999, with a corresponding p-value of 0.963, suggests that there is no significant no significant difference in the mean level of Math performance among students when grouped according to their parents’ highest educational level at the 0.05 significance level. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be concluded that, on average, respondents' level of Math performance did not differ based on their parents’ highest educational attainment.

In contrast to the findings of Abuya et al. (2018), who asserted that higher parental education contributes to positive family interaction patterns, leading to enhanced academic achievement and the development of achievement-oriented attitudes among children over time. Their study posited that parental education and supportive family interactions cultivate positive experiences that shape children's cognitive scripts, beliefs, and values, influencing their academic and achievement-related behaviors in the long term (Abuya et al., 2018).

Moreover, Abuya et al. (2018) found "a positive association between mothers’ education and achievement, with the effects on achievement larger with increased levels of fathers’ education". Similarly, Laranang and Bondo (2020) noted a significant correlation between respondents' appreciation for Mathematics and their mother's occupation. Given that mothers typically prioritize caring for their families, it follows that mothers' occupations have a substantial influence on how much importance is placed on Mathematics education. Most of the respondents' mothers were housewives, suggesting that these mothers were attentive to their children's educational needs and encouraged them to value and study the knowledge acquired in school.

This finding aligns with Recber (2018), who emphasized the significance of a mother’s occupation in students' academic achievement, highlighting its correlation with academic performance, whereas the father’s occupation did not show such a correlation.

Relationship Between Level of Numeracy Skills and Level of Performance in Mathematics

The table 9 on the next page shows the relationship between level of numeracy skills and level of performance.

Table 9. *Relationship Between Level of Numeracy Skills and Level of Performance in Mathematics*

<i>Level of Numeracy Skills</i>	<i>Level of Performance</i>					<i>Total</i>
	<i>Outstanding</i>	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	<i>Satisfactory</i>	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	<i>Did not meet expectation</i>	
Very Proficient	0	0	0	0	0	0
Proficient	3	6	1	0	0	10
Nearly Proficient	26	69	38	7	0	140
Low Proficient	3	22	28	4	0	60
Very Low Proficient	0	0	0	0	0	0
	35	97	67	11	0	210

Computed (G) value: 0.369
P-value: <0.001
Decision: Reject Ho
Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table presents the cross-tabulation between numeracy skills and mathematics performance of students. Most students (140) are nearly proficient in numeracy, with most performing very satisfactorily (69) or satisfactorily (38).

Since the p-value is less than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected. This means there is a statistically

significant relationship between numeracy skills and mathematics performance. This suggests that students with higher numeracy skills are likely to perform better in mathematics

The results showed that there is enough evidence that suggested a correlation between students' Numeracy skill and performance level with p-value of <0.001 ; hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. Which means that the numeracy skill of the respondents affects their performance level in Mathematics.

The study by Ayebo and Dingel (2021) reinforced findings indicating a positive relationship between students' attitudes toward Mathematics and their Mathematics achievement. Descriptive statistics and correlation analyses revealed that students who perceived themselves as performing well in Mathematics tended to achieve higher grades. Similarly, students who believed they grasped mathematical concepts quickly also achieved higher academic success. On the other hand, students who made negative comparisons to their classmates tended to achieve lower grades. Additionally, high-achieving students were more likely to express confidence in their ability to solve challenging mathematical problems.

Moreover, according to the findings of Balala et.al, (2021), early numeracy activities and skills were significantly and favorably connected to attitudes, engagement, and achievement in Mathematics. Also, the results of the mediational analyses revealed that the relationship between early numeracy activities and skills and Mathematics achievement was significantly mediated by confidence in Mathematics. The study's conclusions emphasized the critical part early numeracy activities and abilities play in improving students' attitudes toward, engagement with, and success in Mathematics.

Relationship Between Level of Attitude and Level of Performance in Mathematics

The table 10 on the next page shows the relationship between level of attitude towards mathematics and level of performance.

Table 10. *Relationship Between Level of Attitude and Level of Performance in Mathematics*

Level of Attitude	Level of Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet expectation	
Very Favorable	4	8	7	1	0	20
Favorable	23	44	36	5	0	107
Neither Favorable nor Unfavorable	8	40	24	5	0	77
Unfavorable	0	5	1	0	0	6
Very Unfavorable	0	0	0	0	0	0
	35	97	67	10	0	210

Computed (G) value: 0.065

P-value: 0.495

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table presents the cross-tabulation between level of attitude and mathematics performance of students. Most students (107) are favorable, with most performing very satisfactorily (44) or satisfactorily (36).

The results showed that there was insufficient evidence to suggest a correlation between students' attitudes towards Mathematics and their performance level. The overall significance value of 0.495 was higher than the 0.05 level of significance, leading to acceptance of the null hypothesis. This indicates that the attitude of the respondents towards Mathematics did not significantly impact their performance in the subject.

This finding contrasts with the results from the study by Sunghwan Hwang and Taekwon Son (2021), which demonstrated that students who enjoy studying Mathematics, engage in Mathematics-related activities, believe in the positive outcomes of learning Mathematics (such as success in school and job opportunities), and have confidence in their mathematical abilities are more likely to achieve high Mathematics performance. Moreover, Chen et al. (2018), as cited in the same study, highlighted that students' attitudes towards Mathematics play a crucial role in their cognitive development and can either facilitate or inhibit the acquisition of mathematical knowledge and skills, thereby influencing their overall achievement in the subject.

Similarly, Subia et al. (2018) observed a significant negative correlation between students' attitudes towards Mathematics and their performance in Mathematics I. They reported a strong negative correlation coefficient ($r = -0.940^{**}$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that higher levels of negative attitude towards Mathematics are associated with lower performance in Mathematics I. This suggests that students who maintain a positive attitude towards Mathematics tend to achieve better academic outcomes compared to those with a negative attitude.

Conclusions

Based on the above findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

The study revealed that most Grade 7 learners were male, from low-income families, and graduated from public schools. Additionally, a significant number of learners had parents with higher educational attainment, suggesting that parental education level may play a

role in learners' academic background.

Grade 7 learners generally exhibited a favorable attitude towards Mathematics. However, learners from private schools and those with parents whose educational attainment was at the elementary level displayed a neutral attitude, highlighting potential areas for intervention to improve perceptions of the subject.

The numeracy skills of respondents indicated a nearly proficient level overall. Students from private schools and those whose parents had only an elementary-level education demonstrated lower proficiency, indicating the need for targeted support to bridge gaps in numeracy skills for these groups.

The respondents achieved very satisfactory performance levels in Mathematics overall. However, learners with parents who were elementary graduates performed at a lower satisfactory level, pointing to the potential impact of parental educational background on student achievement.

No significant differences were found in learners' attitudes towards Mathematics when grouped by profile variables, indicating that demographic factors did not significantly influence their attitude toward the subject.

A significant difference in numeracy levels was observed only when grouped by sex, with females showing slightly higher numeracy. Other variables such as family income, type of school, and parental education showed no significant differences, suggesting numeracy levels are generally consistent across these groups.

A significant difference in performance was noted when grouped by sex, with females outperforming males. However, no significant differences were observed for other profile variables, suggesting consistent performance across income levels, school types, and parental education levels.

There was no significant relationship between learners' attitudes toward Mathematics and their performance in the subject, indicating that attitude alone does not directly influence achievement in Mathematics.

A significant positive relationship was found between numeracy levels and Mathematics performance, emphasizing that stronger numeracy skills contribute to higher achievement in Mathematics.

The researcher highly recommends the following:

Educational programs may prioritize resources and support for low-income families to ensure equitable access to learning materials, tutorials, and enrichment activities. Community-based programs or school partnerships can help bridge resource gaps for public school graduates.

Initiatives may target learners with neutral attitudes towards Mathematics, especially those from private schools and with parents of lower educational attainment. These could include engaging teaching strategies, motivational workshops, and real-life applications of Mathematics to make the subject more relatable and appealing.

Specialized numeracy interventions can focus on students from private schools and those whose parents have only an elementary-level education. Remedial programs, peer tutoring, and adaptive learning technologies can help elevate their numeracy proficiency to match their peers.

Schools may design localized workshops or activities to involve parents with lower educational backgrounds in their children's learning. Providing tools and strategies for supporting Mathematics at home can mitigate the impact of parental education on student performance.

Since demographic factors do not significantly influence attitudes, teachers may use inclusive and equitable teaching methods that cater to diverse learners, ensuring that no group is overlooked in Mathematics instruction.

Given the differences in numeracy and performance between male and female learners, the school may provide equal opportunities and encourage participation across genders. Teachers can employ differentiated instruction to address varying strengths and areas for improvement in both genders.

Programs designed to enhance numeracy skills may be emphasized, as they directly impact Mathematics performance. Activities such as problem-solving workshops, mental math exercises, and gamified learning can foster stronger connections between conceptual understanding and application.

Since attitude toward Mathematics does not directly influence performance, further research can explore other factors, such as teaching methodologies, classroom environment, and access to technology, to better understand what drives academic success in Mathematics.

Regular assessments of numeracy skills and performance levels can be conducted to identify students needing additional support. Data-driven strategies can then be implemented to address specific gaps and track progress effectively.

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